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Scribes, sources, and readers:
Using a digital edition to develop understanding of the
Beowulf manuscript

Moving from a source-centric to a reader-centric approach

Early in the Anglo-Saxon period, the role of scribes was conceived of as being source-centred. Their primary responsibility was to the author of a work, and the key indicator of their success was the faithful reproduction of an exemplar. This is clear in, for instance, the illustration of St Matthew in the Lindisfarne Gospels.¹ Matthew receives divine inspiration, coming both from a Christ-like figure behind a curtain and from his human emblem, here apparently angelic to emphasise his channelling of the heavenly word. Further, the scribe of the gospels, by siting Matthew and the other gospel-writers as scribes, makes clear his own aspiration to emulate them: to reproduce their scribal performances just as he imagines the saints authentically reproducing what they saw in the life of Christ. In this model, scribes are either effective thanks to their absolute fidelity, or poor because they mangled their source text due to inattentiveness, incomprehension, or lack of skill. It is against this kind of scribal ineptitude that Ælfric seeks to guard himself when he spells out how certain words ‘sceal beon’ (‘should be’) written.²

But most scribes did not, in fact, endeavour to mechanically reproduce their exemplars: they often ‘sought to interpret a text...to make it more easily accessible to the reader’;³ over time, ‘[t]ranscription was being replaced by transmission’.⁴ That is, the notion of a scribe as the servant of a source or of its author competed with one of a scribe who served the readers instead. In this dynamic, it is not through ineptitude that a scribe fails to reproduce an exemplar: it is through deliberate choice based on an understanding (more or less accurate) of textual meaning and readers’ needs.⁵

This shift in scribal focus from sources to readers was not uncontested. As already noted, authors such as Ælfric sought to defend their work from meddling,

though his concern is more about scribes failing to understand his work than their attempts to recreate it for new readers: incompetence rather than attempted editing. In a letter sent to Ursus of Benevento, however, Hildemar of Corbie attacked the pedagogical role that he felt scribes were assuming. The addition of tonic accents assisting the proper pronunciation of Latin could only be, he felt, ‘propter inertes lectores’ (‘for the benefit of lazy readers’).⁶ In Hildemar’s view, it is a scribe’s role to present the source and the reader’s role to work to approach that source. The text itself should stand still.

On the whole, though, Hildemar lost the battle. Sources were reshaped, incorporating not only word spacing and tonic accents, but ultimately a whole raft of different apparatus designed around readers’ needs. Ultimately, texts were translated and, like the Lindisfarne Gospels themselves, glossed. A reader-centred approach came to dominate the production of text. For modern scholars, this provides an exciting opportunity: many scribal interactions with a text relate directly both to that text’s meaning and how readers accessed or created meaning; or, at least, individual scribes’ conceptions of meaning and its production. That is, if we are to meet Malcolm Parkes’ formidable challenge and seek to see ‘[t]hrough the eyes of scribes and readers’,⁷ a complex approach to manuscripts is necessary: rather than seeing them as late and imperfect records of texts, to which an archaeological approach must be taken, they can be (to some degree) analysed as editions whose presentational choices can, where they are identifiable, offer a valid record of the creation of meaning. Francis Newton has spelt out the methodological challenge this presents: we need, he argues, to

examine the whole not only with our best palaeographical, codicological, art-analytical eye, but also with the other – our best philological, rhetorical, literary, close-reading eye. The two might complement each other.⁸

Approaching Anglo-Saxon manuscripts in this way means attempting to engage with the peculiarities of production rather than seeking to identify them and remove their ‘corrupting’ effects from a text. This approach is one aspect of what has been called ‘the new materiality’ by Michelle Brown.⁹ That is, rather than seeking to identify the corruptions brought in by scribes in order to recover an earlier version of a text, we have an opportunity to treat scribal adjustments as editorial decisions which reflect the needs and uses made of texts by a particular audience in specific places and at specific times. The case has been made more eloquently by Donald Scragg: ‘what happens to a text is just as interesting, ultimately, as where it came from’.¹⁰ Just as Parkes’ ambition results

in Newton's methodological challenge, so Scragg's interest logically leads to a severe standard for manuscript scholarship: Leonard Boyle has argued that '[a]ny mark or drawing or correction or illustration or erasure in a manuscript is part of the history of the transmission of a text and should be recorded and, if necessary, justified and explained'.¹¹

The Nowell codex: scribes and sources

As Josef Klegraf argued some time ago, the Nowell codex is remarkably well placed to support an attempt to address the challenge of identifying and understanding the decisions made by scribes in their production of manuscripts.¹² The codex is more correctly described as the second half of London, British Library MS Cotton Vitellius A. xv, and more widely known as 'the *Beowulf* Manuscript'.¹³ It was produced in the early eleventh century: dated on palaeographical grounds to between 1000 and 1016, but with perhaps some possibility of extending that terminus ad quem to 1025.¹⁴ As part of the Cotton collection, it was damaged in the Ashburnham House fire of 1731: the fire and various stages of restorative work that followed removed all threads, binding information, and prickings from the codex. There are no strong grounds on which to identify its place of production, although it has been very cautiously connected with centres influenced by Wulfstan, indicating London, Worcester, and perhaps York.¹⁵ The known history of the codex begins in 1563, when Laurence Nowell signed what is now the first page with his name and the year. At some point between 1628 and 1638 it came into the possession of Robert Cotton and in his library it was bound together with another, unrelated, document now called the Southwick Codex.¹⁶

As it now stands, the Nowell codex contains five texts, all in Old English, with the first three in prose and the last two in verse:

'The Passion of St Christopher' [hereafter 'St Christopher'];¹⁷

'The Wonders of the East' [hereafter 'Wonders'];¹⁸

'Alexander's Letter to Aristotle' [hereafter 'Alexander'];¹⁹

Beowulf;²⁰

Judith.²¹

There are good reasons for thinking that *Judith* originally preceded 'St Christopher', and that it was itself preceded by another piece of religious verse.²² There may in addition have been another text, perhaps again hagiographical, in between *Judith* and 'St Christopher' which may have been in either verse or

prose. 'Wonders' is illustrated with relatively simple images, and capitals are generally unadorned, with occasional elements of scribal decoration.

Two scribes, usually called Scribe A and Scribe B, worked on the codex.²³ Scribe A copied the three prose texts and the first two thirds of *Beowulf*, up to the middle of poetic line 1939b.²⁴ Scribe B copied the rest of *Beowulf* and *Judith*. As the preceding paragraph implies, this division was probably originally less neat than it appears, as Scribe B's *Judith* originally came before Scribe A's prose pieces. Scribe B writes in a late form of Anglo-Saxon Square Minuscule, which fell out of use in the early eleventh century,²⁵ and Scribe A in an early form of English Vernacular Minuscule which came into favour around the same time.²⁶ Scribe B also makes thirteen corrections to his colleague's work in *Beowulf*.²⁷ The relative age of their hands, the corrections, and that B's work probably originally sandwiched A's, have all supported the widespread assumption that B was the senior partner in the project.

Clarity when discussing the texts is not easy: the manuscript has been re-foliated at least six times, resulting in a complex and confusing set of numbers on many of its recto pages.²⁸ To make things more challenging, different editors have used different foliations.²⁹ That most generally followed is the British Library's preferred system, made in 1884 and written on protective paper frames around each folio: this is used by their online facsimile, and by Malone in his. However, this foliation does not take account of gatherings 2 and 3 having been swapped around and not re-sited, three folios which have been removed from the manuscript, and two folios which have been moved since the numbering was completed. *Beowulf* scholarship is increasingly following the method introduced by Kevin Kiernan, which looks cumbersome but is useful in providing a cross-reference.³⁰ I will follow his system, including British Library numbers in brackets, in the hope that it will make it easier for my discussion of specific manuscript pages to be compared with readings elsewhere.

Despite all of these challenges in discussing it, the Nowell codex is, as noted above, well suited to analyses of scribal decision making in the production of vernacular texts. It offers examples of different prose texts and a poem copied by the same scribe, different poetic texts copied by another scribe, and a single text (*Beowulf*) copied by both scribes. If there are clear consistencies between the texts copied by a single hand, we can work towards the conclusion that he is flattening the texts into an aspect of his own style; if, by contrast, there are distinct differences in elements of the different texts he copies, we can take this as evidence that he is preserving exemplar forms with some degree of fidelity. Both of these tentative conclusions can be tested by comparing the work of the different

scribes on the same text. If Scribe A has a ‘default’ style, that should be apparent in all of the texts he copies, and should contrast with Scribe B’s on at least some points when they are copying the same text.

An inversion of this approach, focusing on the changes scribes have failed to make, has long been used to test for the origin of texts. As one example among many, medial *-io-* in place of *-eo-* occurs infrequently in ‘Wonders’, ‘Alexander’, and *Beowulf*, but not at all in ‘St Christopher’ or *Judith*.³¹ That neither scribe uses *-io-* in all of the texts they copy has been taken to demonstrate that it was an original feature in the three texts where it does appear and to argue that ‘St Christopher’ and *Judith* may have had a similar origin;³² and at different times to argue for the greater fidelity of one or the other scribe.³³ Similarly, I have argued elsewhere that the variation in style of marginal capitals between the three prose texts suggests that they are taken from different exemplars; that, taken with the similarity in style of marginal capitals used by the scribes in *Beowulf*, suggests that both scribes are, to some extent, seeking to imitate the style of capitalisation in their exemplar manuscripts.³⁴ By contrast, significant differences in the use of minor capitals by the scribes in *Beowulf* makes it likely that these have been introduced with some degree of scribal discretion.³⁵ Similarities in the style of capitalisation in ‘St Christopher’ and *Judith* can be brought together with the linguistic and codicological evidence to strengthen the case for those texts coming from the same source. The Nowell codex scribes can thus be seen to have, or to perceive themselves as having, a relatively complex relationship with their sources: they are both, to a degree, copying language and appearance with at least an attempt at fidelity that might have pleased Ælfric; they are also presenting new relationships between texts not previously conjoined and bringing some elements of their own interpretative presentation into play. With a very few exceptions traceable to royal or religious commission,³⁶ so little is known about the process of commissioning and producing Anglo-Saxon textual collections that it is difficult or even impossible to make judgements about the motivations behind these negotiations with source documents. But given the concerns of the period with re-presenting texts for readers as briefly discussed above, it seems reasonable to assume that any conscious choices made about presentation were made with readers in mind.

The Nowell codex: scribes and readers

If the eleventh century scribes were working to re-present exemplars for their readers, and if they were deliberately bringing together disparate texts in one production, their editorial sensibilities have not found favour. Editions of the

texts of the codex have not generally regarded it as a valid grouping. They have, in fact, proved so unappealing as a collection that the five texts have been produced together only twice: in the Nowell codex some time after the year 1000 and in the *Dumbarton Oaks Medieval Library* series in 2010. Between these two editions lie a thousand years during which, in keeping with the general approach of scholarship to Anglo-Saxon literature, prose and poetry were kept fiercely apart and in which neither the two poems nor the three prose pieces are seen to engage with one another. Editors of *Beowulf* have regularly presented that text as an isolated masterpiece, or footnoted by *The Finnsburh Fragment*. This poetic text is completely unrelated in manuscript terms: it is included because it gives more information about a digression in the ‘main’ poem. In 1924, the prose texts were edited together based on their manuscript association, but subsequent editions of ‘St Christopher’ and of ‘Wonders’ (listed above as footnotes 17 and 18) have not seen the need to refer to the rest of the codex. Andy Orchard brought ‘Alexander’ and ‘Wonders’ together again, but did not use the Nowell version of ‘Wonders’ and separated the two texts with the Latin version of ‘Alexander’. His discussion of the interrelationship of the Nowell codex texts actually says a great deal more about the ‘Liber Monstrorum’, unrelated in manuscript terms, than ‘Wonders’, and has only brief introductory discussion of ‘St Christopher’. Even Robert Fulk’s edition for the *Dumbarton Oaks* series, noted above as bringing the manuscript texts back together again, follows Orchard in preferring the fuller version of ‘Wonders’ witnessed in London BL Cotton MS Tiberius B.v, and he includes *The Finnsburh Fragment*, presumably because *Beowulf* is incomplete without it. The first appendix of the standard scholarly edition of *Beowulf* contains thirty-three ‘Parallels (Analogues and Illustrative Passages)’, but there is no mention of the other texts of the Nowell codex.

The earliest transcriptions and facsimiles of the texts of the manuscript form another branch of this separatist trend. Franciscus Junius transcribed *Judith* in c. 1605, into what is now Bodley MS Junius 105, and Grímur Jónsson Thorkelin famously commissioned one copy of *Beowulf* (which aspires to reproduce manuscript presentation) and himself produced another in 1787. In 1882, Julius Zupitza produced the first photographic facsimile from the codex, of *Beowulf* alone. ‘Wonders’ has enjoyed a similarly isolated editorial reception: in 1929, M. R. James edited the three extant insular versions together, including reduced size facsimiles of the Nowell Codex images; in 1983, it again featured in a facsimile, as a companion piece to that in London BL MS Cotton Tiberius B.v.³⁷ The first attempt to reproduce the document produced by its scribes was published in 1963, as a result of the perceived need to ensure ‘survival amid the dangers which an

atomic age brings to all our most treasured possessions', edited by Kemp Malone for the Early English Manuscripts in Facsimile series.³⁸ Fine as Malone's edition is, it retains the proportions of the series and so is both cumbersome and expensive; retaining the size of both the series and the codex means that it has to present two manuscript sides on each facsimile page. For the student wishing to see 'through the eyes of scribes and readers', the task was difficult indeed.

More recently, Malone's edition has been supplemented by two full facsimiles: Kevin Kiernan's *Electronic 'Beowulf'* and the British Library's 'Digitised Manuscripts' online presentation. The use of digital editions is fraught with difficulties as well as opportunities,³⁹ and there is no space here to discuss the relative merits of these very different resources, which could be summarised by the brilliantly high zoom of the British Library's edition, and the crucial discussion provided in Kiernan's.⁴⁰ But it is, of course, important to remember that reading a manuscript onscreen may allow us to attempt to look through the eyes of scribes and readers, but does not bring us any nearer to touching with their hands, smelling with their nostrils, or hearing with their ears.⁴¹ What it does enable, however, is a kind of democratisation that Kiernan has hailed as enabling us 'as a scholarly community, rather than as an individual scholar with special access to a rare manuscript, to reevaluate the evidence'.⁴² Digital editions could thus be seen as a modern form of the tonic accents and textual apparatus deplored by Hildemar: 'propter inertes lectores' in that they are easy to use and access and thus support very close study of specific manuscript features: through them, 'lazy' modern readers are able to approach the scribes and the sources they worked from as never before.

The relationship between the scribes and source of *Beowulf*

As an example, it is possible to use the digital editions of the Nowell codex to engage with an important argument for the dating of *Beowulf*. Michael Lapidge has influentially argued that the errors in the copying of the poem are best explained by an eighth century exemplar being misunderstood by scribes. He proposed that the source copy was

a manuscript in Anglo-Saxon set minuscule script, written before c. 750, the scribe of which...employed occasional cursive letterforms, such as open *a* and the ligatures *ec* and *et*, and frequently, if not consistently, retained *d* to represent the interdental fricative.⁴³

Lapidge's argument is based on the types of single-letter error that occur most

frequently in the copying of *Beowulf*. He identified errors conservatively, effectively partially reconstructing a ‘perfect’ copy with the emendations made by the majority of editors of the poem. His proposition is that the regularity with which errors are made in copying specific letters suggests that the scribes of *Beowulf* found those particularly hard to read;⁴⁴ from this, he proposes set minuscule as the hand in which those letters are hardest to read. In so doing, as he notes, Lapidge is using a relatively blunt instrument: it is not possible to know how many times the text was copied between his putative exemplar and the sole extant text we have.⁴⁵ So he cannot demonstrate that the Nowell codex scribes were working from a very early exemplar: indeed, he speculatively postulates a three-stage transmission, with his misreadings occurring in a pre-Nowell late-ninth or early-tenth century scriptorium. Lapidge’s interest is in tracing the source of *Beowulf*, not describing what took place in the production of the Nowell codex.

Using a digital edition to consider all alterations made to a text and comparing the texts with one another, it is possible to approach this more precise (if less significant) question of how the Nowell codex scribes worked with their copy-texts. As has been discussed in detail elsewhere, the scribes themselves make a very large number of corrections to *Beowulf*; less frequently discussed is the large number of corrections they make to the other texts of the manuscript.⁴⁶ As Kiernan suggests, the digital editions have enabled me to revisit these errors, in the course of which I have identified 65 scribal corrections to the prose texts, 112 scribal corrections to Scribe A’s work on *Beowulf*, 67 corrections to Scribe B’s work on *Beowulf*, and 14 corrections to his work on *Judith*. This gives a total of 258 scribal corrections in the codex, with 179 in *Beowulf*.⁴⁷ Of these, to the best of my knowledge, 24 across the three prose texts, 18 in Scribe A’s *Beowulf*, 10 in Scribe B’s work on *Beowulf*, and 5 in *Judith* have not been noted in other scholarship.⁴⁸ Scribal corrections do not show us the relationship between the Nowell codex and Lapidge’s early source-text. However, far more clearly than most scribal activity, they demonstrate conscious decision-making and show us both what the scribes themselves thought was challenging in their exemplar, and what they felt their reproduced text should look like. As Neidorf notes, ‘the final scribes might only be guilty of preserving errors’ and not of originally producing them: corrections, though, almost certainly show a movement towards the exemplar text.⁴⁹

In the case of some corrections, this is challenging for editors. As I have discussed elsewhere, at poetic line 1981 Scribe B clearly inserts the word ‘side’, producing the unalliterative line ‘geond þæt side reced hæreðes dohtor...’ (‘through

that broad hall, Hæreth’s daughter...’).⁵⁰ There is little challenge in identifying an alternative alliterative adjective: **heah** is used most frequently. Yet this was certainly not a slip of the pen: it is a deliberate correction and, judging by the shade of ink, was made later than the first stage of writing. This strongly suggests that the exemplar for the Nowell codex scribes had (or seemed to have) **side** in the first position;⁵¹ in turn, this strongly suggests that their exemplar was not a perfect copy of the text, and was therefore perhaps not ‘original’.

Figure 1: Table showing single letter changes made by the scribes of *Beowulf*.

More pertinent in addressing Lapidge’s argument is the frequency of single letter corrections made by the scribes, as shown in Figure 1 above. Excluding corrections to whole words and insertions of omitted letters, but including alterations to or from a pair of ligatured letters, I count sixty-one places in *Beowulf* where the scribes felt they had made a mistake in the category Lapidge explored. Thirty-eight of these are in the work of Scribe A, and twenty-three in the work of Scribe B. Given the relative proportions of the poem they copied, this makes Scribe B more prone to single letter confusions than his colleague which, in Lapidge’s terms, might suggest that he found the exemplar more challenging than the younger man. Forty-four are unique: that is, they occur only once in this sample. As an example, while *a* is changed three times in the text as a whole, on one occasion it is altered to *e*, once to *n*, and once to *ū*: in my analysis, this counts as three different alterations because the misread letter is different in each case. Such a large number of one-off misreadings immediately suggests that errors were more frequently caused by inattention or a low quality exemplar, rather than a consistent difficulty in reading particular letters.

Six alterations occur more than once: $\delta \rightarrow d$; $e \rightarrow a$; $e \rightarrow \text{æ}$; $e \rightarrow o$; $m \rightarrow n$; $r \rightarrow n$. Of these, the last three occur only twice; $\delta \rightarrow d$ occurs four times, as does $e \rightarrow a$; $e \rightarrow \text{æ}$ occurs three times. It is worth noting that examination of scribal corrections to a manuscript, no matter how effective the facsimile, cannot show all changes. For both scribes, a correction of $d \rightarrow \delta$ would be simply a matter of crossing the ascender and would only be detectable if a different shade of ink were used. Other micro-corrections, such as the erasure of part of a stroke to convert $m \rightarrow in$ or $\text{þ} \rightarrow b$, are identifiable: many other similar corrections, of course, may well exist but be missed in my examination. So these numbers should not be regarded as definitive.

Clearly, of prime interest are the four instances coinciding with one of Lapidge's key errors: the change of $\delta \rightarrow d$. His other categories are the confusion of a and u , of which there are no instances though there is a change of u to an ; confusion of r and n , which occurs twice; confusion of p and p [wynn], which occurs once (with confusion of p [wynn] with p or þ occurring twice); confusion of c and t when in ligature with e , which occurs once. All told, then, just eight out of sixty-one scribal corrections (13%) conform to the hypothesis that the Nowell codex scribes were copying from an eighth century exemplar and facing the challenges Lapidge proposes. These are much more explicable as simply random errors: even the relatively frequent confusion of d and δ does not imply a particular pattern, as it is such an easy mistake to make whatever hand is being used.

It is worth reiterating that this brief discussion does not disprove Lapidge's postulated eighth century copy of the poem. If one accepts the hypothesis of a perfect originary exemplar existing at some point in *Beowulf*'s history, it remains the case that some letters written in set minuscule could have been misread by a later scribe to produce some of the errors preserved in the Nowell version. However, there is no correspondence between the pattern of errors that the scribes themselves identified in their work, and the pattern of errors Lapidge identified between the *Beowulf* preserved in Nowell and an editorial ideal text. This makes it likely that Scribe A and Scribe B were not the men responsible for introducing the majority of errors in our text of *Beowulf*, and almost certain that they were not struggling to read an eighth century exemplar.

Conclusion

A wide-ranging discussion is necessarily somewhat cursory in its consideration of some quite complex concepts. But what I hope has been demonstrated here is, first, that scribes made interesting and sometimes complex negotiations between their sources and their readers. Second, the nuances of scribal re-presentation

for their readers are not as inaccessible as was once the case: the increased availability of digital facsimiles enables even the laziest and most excluded of modern readers to observe the details of scribal activity. Third, this in turn allows us as modern readers to engage with and analyse scribal negotiations and, through them, to approach both sources and readers from the Anglo-Saxon period who otherwise remain shrouded in anonymity.

Notes

1 London, British Library, Cotton MS Nero D.iv, *Lindisfarne Gospels* (Lindisfarne, or Holy Island, 698–721), fol. 25v.

2 See in general Donald G. Scragg, ‘Ælfric’s Scribes’, in *Essays for Joyce Hill on Her Sixtieth Birthday*, ed. by Mary Swan (Leeds, 2006), 179–89, throughout, with examples of Ælfric’s own fastidious approach to orthography at p. 181 including two instances of the ‘seal beon’ phrase, and some particular comments on the scribes’ responses to Ælfric pp. 185–6.

3 Malcolm Parkes, *Their Hands Before Our Eyes: A Closer Look at Scribes*, The Lyell Lectures Delivered at the University of Oxford 1999 (Aldershot, 2008), p. 67; Cf. his comments in *Pause and Effect: An Introduction to the History of Punctuation in the West* (Ashgate, 1992), 97–107.

4 Michelle P. Brown, *The Book and the Transformation of Britain c. 550–1050: A Study in Written and Visual Literacy and Orality* The Sanders Lectures in Bibliography, Cambridge University Library, 2009 (London: The British Library, 2011), p. 30, referring to seventh century Ireland; Cf. p. 77 where she finds ‘the orality of recitation... transcending the copying of exemplars in the masculine voice’ in different manuscripts copied for female communities.

5 In ‘Presenting Poetry: Scribal control over Old English poetic texts’, at ‘Liminal Networks: Western Palaeography to c. 1100’ at KCL 3 June 2014, I have discussed some different types of scribal performance, attempting to distinguish between alteration of text undertaken effectively and ineffectively; and between that done deliberately and accidentally. Erik Kwakkel argues for a ‘tight relationship between a manuscript’s palaeographical and codicological features, and the culture in which the object was produced and used’ in ‘Writing in Context: Introduction’, *Writing in Context: Insular Manuscript Culture 500–1200*, ed. by Erik Kwakkel, Studies in Medieval and Renaissance Book Culture (Leiden: Leiden University Press, 2013), 15–20, p. 15, and many of the essays therein proceed from this position. As will be apparent from the notes below, my thinking on the production and use of manuscripts is deeply indebted to the work of Kwakkel and his contributors.

6 Quoted by Leonard Boyle, O. P., in ‘*Vox Paginae*’: *An Oral Dimension of Texts*, *Unione Internazionale degli Istituti di Archeologia Storia e Storia dell’Arte in Roma, Conferenze 16* (Rome, 1999), p. 29

7 *Their Hands*, title to chapter 8, pp. 127–45.

8 ‘A Giant Among Scribes: Colophon and Ideological Programme in the Eadui Gospels’, in Kwakkel, ed., *Writing in Context*, 127–49, p. 129. Cf. Michelle Brown in the same volume, ‘Mercian Manuscripts: The Implications of the Staffordshire Hoard, Other Recent Discoveries, and the “New Materiality”’: 23–64, p. 29.

9 Brown, 'Mercian Manuscripts', p. 31. It is worth bearing in mind Teresa Webber's caution that 'manuscripts, even the most complex compilations, are often only tacit witnesses to the reception of texts' and 'Medieval manuscripts also rarely reveal the meanings construed at a detailed level by readers from the texts they contain', both in 'English Manuscripts in the Century after the Norman Conquest: Continuity and Change in the Palaeography of Books and Book Collections', *Writing in Context*, 185–228, p. 204.

10 'Ælfric's Scribes', p. 186.

11 'Vox Paginæ', pp. 31–2.

12 Klegraf, 'Testing faithful copying in the *Beowulf* Manuscript', in *Essays on the English Language and Applied Linguistics on the Occasion of Gerhard Nickel's 60th Birthday*, ed. by Josef Klegraf and Dietrich Nehls (Heidelberg: Julius Groos Verlag, 1988), 206–220, p. 206.

13 Facsimiles are *The Nowell Codex (British Museum Cotton Vitellius A.xv. Second MS)*, ed. by K. Malone (Copenhagen, 1963), who discusses the naming pp. 11–12 and n.3; *The Electronic 'Beowulf' 3.0*, ed. by K. Kiernan (London, 2011); British Library, 'Digitised Manuscripts Online', online since 11th February 2013, last accessed 29th October 2014. Kevin Kiernan argued that 'the *Beowulf* manuscript' was originally a separate codex containing that poem alone, in '*Beowulf* and the *Beowulf* Manuscript' (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 1981, revised edition 1996, 1999 reprint), at e.g. pp. 8, 9, 193, but he has not been broadly followed and no longer holds that position (pers. corr.); the term is widely used to refer to the codex as a whole.

14 The most authoritative palaeographical dating is that by David Dumville, who gives this range in '*Beowulf* Come Lately: Some Notes on the Palaeography of the Nowell Codex', in *Archiv für das Studium der Neueren Sprachen*, 225 (1988), 49–63. Compare Peter Stokes' suggestion that rigid boundaries based on palaeographical rules are risky, *English Vernacular Minuscule from Æthelred to Cnut circa 990–circa 1035* (Cambridge, 2014), p. 198. Neil Ker gave a broader range, from 975–1025, *Catalogue of Manuscripts Containing Anglo-Saxon* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1957), §216, but few would now place the codex earlier than 1000. Kiernan, '*Beowulf* Manuscript' sees production post-1016 likely on historical grounds and has recently been followed by Elaine Treharne, who proposed 1020 as the most likely date in 'Invisible Things in London, British Library, MS Cotton Vitellius A.xv' at the 49th International Congress on Medieval Studies §263, Kalamazoo 2014.

15 So, very tentatively, Stokes, *Vernacular Minuscule* n.66, p. 94; Cf. pp. 99–102 which discuss Wulfstanian manuscripts; Kenneth Sisam, 'The Compilation of the *Beowulf* Manuscript', in *Studies in the History of Old English Literature* (Oxford, 1953), 65–96, p. 95, proposes London as most likely and is followed by Eric Stanley in 'The Date of *Beowulf*: Some Doubts and No Conclusions', in *The Dating of 'Beowulf'*, ed. by Colin Chase (Toronto, 1997), 197–211, p. 211.

16 Kemp Malone was the first to use these names for the codices in *Nowell Codex*.

17 The standard edition of 'St Christopher' is "'The Passion of Saint Christopher'", ed. P. Pulsiano, in *Early Medieval English Texts and Interpretations: Studies Presented to Donald G. Scragg*, ed. by E. Treharne and S. Rosser (Tempe, 2002). All of the texts of the manuscript are edited in a readers' edition as *The 'Beowulf' Manuscript*, ed. by R. D. Fulk (London, 2010). The three prose texts have been transcribed together in *Three Old English Prose Texts in MS Cotton Vitellius A. xv: 'Letter of Alexander the Great', 'Wonders of the East', 'Life of St Christopher'*, ed. by Stanley Rypins (London, 1924). Joseph McGowan is currently working to complete a new edition of the prose texts edited by himself and the late Phillip Pulsiano but this is unlikely to be available for some time.

18 The standard edition of the Nowell codex 'Wonders' is that edited by Asa Mittman

and Susan Kim in *Inconceivable Beasts: The 'Wonders of the East' in the 'Beowulf' Manuscript* (Tempe, 2013); the text is also edited (in a form less faithful to this codex) in Andy Orchard, *Pride and Prodigies: Studies in the Monsters of the 'Beowulf'-Manuscript* (London, 1995). I use Orchard's section numbers throughout. It is also edited by Rypins, *Prose Texts*, and Fulk, *Manuscript*. Fulk, Orchard, and Rypins all supplement the Nowell version with details from BL **MS Cotton** Tiberius B. v, with notes on the variances. All of the texts in the 'Wonders' tradition are edited together in Ann Knock's *'Wonders of the East': A Synoptic Edition of 'The Letter of Pharasmanes' and the Old English and Old Picard Translations* (unpublished University of London PhD thesis, 1981). In addition to the facsimiles of the whole manuscript noted above, facsimiles specifically of 'Wonders' are in *An Eleventh-Century Anglo-Saxon Illustrated Miscellany (British Library Cotton Tiberius B. v part 1)*, ed. by Patrick McGurk, D. N. Dumville, M. R. Godden, and A. E. Knock (Copenhagen, 1983), and in *The Marvels of the East: a Full Reproduction of the Three Known Copies, with Introduction and Notes*, ed. by M. R. James (Oxford, 1929).

19 The standard edition of 'Alexander' is that in Orchard, *Pride and Prodigies*. It is also edited by Rypins, *Prose Texts*, and Fulk, *Manuscript*.

20 There are many editions of *Beowulf*. The standard edition is *Klaeber's 'Beowulf': Fourth Edition*, ed. by R. D. Fulk, R. E. Bjork and J. D. Niles (Toronto, 2008). Kiernan's edition included in *Electronic 'Beowulf'* has a different line numbering system and is a useful, highly conservative reinterpretation. It is also edited by E. V. K. Dobbie in *'Beowulf' and 'Judith'*, ASPR IV (New York, 1953), and in Fulk, *Manuscript*.

21 The most recent edition of *Judith* is that edited by Mark Griffith (Exeter, 1997). It is also included in Dobbie, *'Beowulf' and 'Judith'*, and in Fulk, *Manuscript*.

22 Most comprehensively argued for by Peter Lucas, 'The Place of *Judith* in the *Beowulf* Manuscript', *RES* n.s., 41 (1990), 463–78, who has broadly been followed. Kiernan concurs with Malone's suggestion that *Judith* was not originally part of the codex at all, and was joined with the end of *Beowulf* at some point in the Renaissance by Nowell or Robert Cotton. I am grateful to Professor Kiernan for discussing this with me and for sharing his piece on the place of *Judith* in the manuscript, 'The Reformed Nowell Codex and the *Beowulf* Manuscript' (unpublished); see also Malone, *Nowell Codex*, pp. 17 and 119.

23 That 'Alexander' is in the same hand as the start of *Beowulf* was identified in 1913 by Walter Sedgefield in his *Beowulf*, second edition (Manchester, 1913) p. xiv; Sisam identified that the same hand produced all of the prose texts in 1916 in 'The *Beowulf* Manuscript', in his *Studies*, 61–64, and Rypins called attention to the identification and its significance in 1924, *Three Prose Texts*, pp. xi–xiii.

24 Andy Orchard, *A Critical Companion to 'Beowulf'* (Cambridge: D. S. Brewer, 2003; 2004 paperback reprint), p. 22 notes that relatively abrupt scribal handovers are not particularly uncommon in the period and gives a range of examples; Cf. Brown, *Book and Transformation*, p. 54, where she notes that in the Barberini Gospels (Vatican MS, Barb. lat. 570, c. 800) the scribes seem to have attempted to 'blend their style at the places where they handed over to one another', and Richard Gameson who finds that even 'words are sometimes split across contributions' in manuscripts from the late tenth to early twelfth centuries, 'Anglo-Saxon Scribes and Scriptoria' in *The Cambridge History of the Book in Britain Volume 1 c. 400–1100*, ed. Richard Gameson (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), 94–120, pp. 109–10.

25 David Dumville, 'English Square Minuscule Script: The Mid-Century Phases', *ASE*, 23 (1994), 133–64 is the clearest and most authoritative discussion of the hand.

26 Stokes, *Vernacular Minuscule*, is the most recent and comprehensive study of this hand. The two hands are discussed in all major analyses of the manuscript and of *Beowulf*; see for instance Fulk et al, *Klaeber's Fourth* p. xxix; Malone, *Nowell Codex*, pp.

17–20; Stokes, *Vernacular Minuscule*, Table 8, p. 95; Dumville, ‘*Beowulf* Come Lately’, p. 50.

27 *Klaeber’s Fourth* does not accept (or just does not note) fol. 167 (BL170)v.10, *ferþe* → *ferhþe* with a superscript *h*, giving a list of the twelve corrections the editors see as n. 1, p. xxxiii. Cf. Orchard, *Companion*, n. 147, p. 46, who lists all thirteen and who includes them in his appendix of all the corrections he sees being made to *Beowulf* in Andy Orchard, ‘Reading *Beowulf* Now and Then’, *Selima* 12 (2003–04), 49–81. Of the thirteen, ten are inserted letters and three are substitutions. These are relatively easy to identify because (unlike Scribe A when he corrects himself), Scribe B always uses insertion marks and his letterforms are distinct. It is possible that erasures or even emendations may be his work as well but of course they are much harder, if not impossible, to distinguish from those made by Scribe A. Nick Doane sees ‘a dozen emendations B made to A’s work’, ‘*Beowulf* and Scribal Performance’, in *Unlocking the Wordhoard: Studies in Memory of Edward B. Irving Jr*, ed. by M. C. Amodio and Katherine O’Brien O’Keefe (London: University of Toronto Press, 2003), 62–75, p. 72: the one example he gives is *sce deninge* to *scedenigge* on 167 (BL170) r.1, which I do not see though the first *g* is certainly poorly written and may be emended. It is not B’s usual practice to erase and overwrite, even in his own work. Cf. Leonard Neidorf, ‘Scribal Errors of Proper Names in the *Beowulf* Manuscript’, *ASE* 42 (2013), 249–69, pp. 258–59, who sees a correction here but does not attribute it to Scribe B; Neidorf refers to ‘the scribe’, implying that he sees Scribe A’s hand here.

28 Kiernan provides a detailed discussion of these foliations and his evidence for each of them, ‘*Beowulf*’ *Manuscript*, pp. 91–110.

29 Malone gives an overwhelmingly full table of the variant foliations, *Nowell Codex*, p. 14; Orchard provides a concordance of sorts to the foliation of *Beowulf* alone, *Companion*, Appendix 1, pp. 268–73.

30 Most notably, Andy Orchard follows it in *Companion*. Kiernan explains his system ‘*Beowulf*’ *Manuscript*, pp. 6–7.

31 Sisam, ‘Compilation’, discusses a range of linguistic features including *-io-* versus *-eo-*; Cf. also Rypins, *Three Prose Texts*, Malone, *Nowell Codex*, and Lucas, ‘Place of *Judith*’.

32 See for instance Sisam ‘Compilation’, pp. 68 and 93.

33 Rypins and Klegraf find Scribe A more faithful to his exemplar; Klaeber, Hulbert (in ‘The Accuracy of the B-Scribe of *Beowulf*’, *PMLA* 43 (1928):, 1196–99), and Kiernan find Scribe B a more reliable witness. See also Orchard, *Companion*, pp. 23–8.

34 ‘Manuscript stability and literary corruption: our failure to understand the *Beowulf* manuscript’, *Quaestio Insularis* (forthcoming).

35 ‘Capital Indications: How Scribe A thought readers should engage with the Nowell codex’, in *Proceedings from the Conference on Language, Culture and Society in Russian / English Studies at IES 5–6 August 2014* (forthcoming).

36 As, for instance, the York Gospels which Wulfstan certainly owned and which may have been commissioned for him by Cnut; Brown, *Book and Transformation*, offers an interpretation of Cnut’s message in commissioning the text at p. 143; see also in general on the commissioning of books Richard Gameson, ‘Book decoration in England, c. 871–c. 1100’ in *History of the Book* (2012), 249–93, esp. pp. 253–58 and 274–78.

37 McGurk et al, *Illustrated Miscellany*.

38 The quotation is from Bertram Colgrave’s ‘Preface’, *The Nowell Codex*, p. 7.

39 The most comprehensive published analysis of the challenges of digital resources is probably the collection of essays in Jonathon Wilcox, ed., *Scraped, Stroked, and Bound: Materially Engaged Readings of Medieval Manuscripts*, Utrecht Studies in Medieval Literacy (Turnhout: Brepols, 2013), see especially the pieces by Wilcox ‘Introduction:

The Philology of Smell’, 1–13, p. 3, and Gary Frost, ‘Material Quality of Medieval Bookbindings’, 129–34, pp. 133–4. A number of sessions and individual papers at the 49th International Congress on Medieval Studies Kalamazoo 2014 focused on discussions of digitalisation and there will no doubt be much more material published in the coming years.

40 For reviews of Kiernan, see W. Kilbride, ‘Whose Beowulf is it anyway? Review of *Electronic Beowulf* [CD-Rom]’, *Internet Archaeology* 9 (2000); Toby Burrows, ‘The Electronic *Beowulf*’, and: *The ‘Piers Plowman’ Electronic Archive*, vol. 1: Corpus Christi College, Oxford, MS 201 (F), and: *Ductus: A History of Handwriting*, and: *The Book of Kells* (review), *Parergon* 18 (2001), 156–60. I am not aware of any reviews of the British Library’s website.

41 See also Wilcox, ‘Introduction’. Wilcox develops these ideas further in ‘The Sensory Cost of Remediation, or, Sniffing in the Gutter of the Blickling Homilies’ in *Sensory Perception in the Medieval World: Manuscripts, Texts, and Other Material Matters*, eds. S. C. Thomson & Michael Bintley, Utrecht Studies in Medieval Literacy (Turnhout: Brepols, forthcoming).

42 Kevin Kiernan, ‘The ‘nathwylc’ Scribe and the ‘nathwylc’ Text of *Beowulf*’, in *Poetry, Place, and Gender: Studies in Medieval Culture in Honor of Helen Damico*, ed. Catherine E. Karkov, Medieval Institute Publications (Kalamazoo, 2009), 98–131, p. 98.

43 Michael Lapidge, ‘The Archetype of *Beowulf*’, *ASE* 29 (2000), 5–41, p. 34. His analysis has not been uncontroversial, with important refutations by Eric Stanley, who questions the significance of Lapidge’s statistics in comparison with other Old English texts, as well as interrogating the likelihood of single letter confusions arising from the difficulty of reading those letters rather than other and varied sources in ‘Paleographical and Textual Deep Waters: <a> for <u> and <u> for <a>, <d> for <ð> and <ð> for <d> in Old English’, *A Quarterly Journal of Short Notes and Queries* (2002), 64–72; and Roberta Frank, who broadly follows Lapidge on this point in a general questioning of critical certainties on the dating of *Beowulf* in ‘A Scandal in Toronto: The Dating of *Beowulf*’ a Quarter Century On’, *Speculum* 82 (2007), 843–64, see esp. p. 857. These have in turn been partially refuted by George Clark, who argues that Stanley’s mini-case study of the Arundel Psalter does not undermine Lapidge’s case, though he does not address Stanley’s and Frank’s more general concerns, in ‘The Date of *Beowulf* and the Arundel Psalter Gloss’, *MP* 106.4 (2009), 677–85. Lapidge’s argumentation has proved widely influential in discussions of *Beowulf* and of other manuscript transmissions, as in for instance Leonard Neidorf’s ‘Scribal Errors’ at e.g. p. 250.

44 As discussed further below, the key frequent letter confusions he focuses on are those between *a* and *u*; *r* and *n*; *p* and *þ* [wynn]; *c* and *t* when in ligature with *e*; *d* and *ð*. He finds ‘nearly forty’ out of sixty total putative single-letter errors accounted for by this hypothesis, p. 35.

45 ‘Archetype’, p. 36.

46 For discussion of scribal corrections to *Beowulf*, see Kiernan, ‘*Beowulf*’ Manuscript and Orchard, ‘Reading *Beowulf*’; the latter has an appendix with a full list of corrections Orchard sees being made to *Beowulf*; Malone, *Nowell Codex*, lists scribal corrections in his detailed commentary on each text, pp. 32–114. Griffith discusses corrections in his textual notes to *Judith*. Klegraf comments on some corrections in ‘Testing’, p. 213, as does Leonard Neidorf in ‘Scribal Errors’, see esp. p. 269. Rypins notes some corrections to the prose texts in *Three Prose Texts*. I am profoundly grateful to Joe McGowan, who shared the late Phillip Pulsiano’s notes made on the prose texts from an examination of the manuscript: these include a number of errors unnoted by Rypins or myself and are incorporated into my attempt to fully document all corrections in the codex.

47 My list of corrections in the codex was shared as a handout at ‘Mistakes made, unmade, and remade: a millennium of making the Nowell codex’ in ‘Un/making mistakes

in medieval media' at International Congress on Medieval Studies, Kalamazoo 8–11 May 2014, and will be included as an appendix to my UCL PhD thesis, 'Towards a reception history of *Beowulf* in the context of the Nowell codex'.

48 Which is not to say they have not been seen before: Kiernan, for instance, suggests that there are 'about 180 intelligent corrections' made by the scribes in *Beowulf*, but does not have a full list, *'Beowulf' Manuscript* p. 142 and pers. corr..

49 'Scribal Errors', p. 253; Cf. Orchard, *Companion*, p. 47.

50 At manuscript 173 (BL176) v.4. My discussion is in 'Manuscript stability'.

51 By contrast, A. N. Doane, '*Beowulf* and Scribal Performance', p. 68, argues both that Scribe B was sufficiently 'attuned to the verse' to make improvised changes to the text, and that this insertion is neither from the exemplar nor acceptable; I do not follow his logic.

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